

To Act or Not to Act: An Essentialist Meaning in Dave Hanson's *Waiting for Waiting for Godot*

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Abstract: *Waiting for Waiting for Godot* (2016) is a biographical and award-winning two-act play, a parody of Beckett's seminal work *Waiting for Godot* (1953). It is one of the most renowned works of the new-generation American playwrights by actor and comedian Dave C. Hanson, who is relatively unknown to scholars. Having used the text in my courses, on January 30, 2024, I contacted playwright Hanson and asked him questions to comprehend the play better and enrich this study with his invaluable comments. Accordingly, I received Hanson's answers to the questions by email on February 6, 2024. It has a discernible plot, so it somehow orients the audience. It embraces essentialism and uncertainty while seeking meaning. To existentialism, humans first exist, then construct their values and personalities by their actions in a disinterested world that they have been thrown out of. According to essentialism, human beings have an essence that differentiates them from other things. Most absurd plays, including *Waiting for Godot*, directly or indirectly examine and question the futility of seeking meaning in a meaningless life and irrational world; the issues the absurd playwrights raise fall into the scope of existentialist philosophy. However, this article aims to explore the essentialist meaning of *WFWFG* by digging into an essentialist meaning through the dialogues extracted from the play, giving the audience a different reading perspective.

Anahtar Sözcükler:

Godot'yu Beklerkeni Beklerken

Dave C. Hanson

Özsellik

Anlam

Varoluşçuluk

Dave Hanson'ın *Godot'yu Beklerkeni Beklerken* Oyununda Özsel Anlam Arayışı

Özet: *Godot'yu Beklerkeni Beklerken* (2016) Beckett'in kült eseri *Godot'yu Beklerken*'in (1953) bir parodisi olarak kaleme alınan ödüllü, iki perdeden oluşan biyografik bir oyundur. Söz konusu oyun, akademik çevrelerde görece az bilinen, Amerikalı yeni nesil oyun yazarı, oyuncu ve komedyen Dave C. Hanson'un en ünlü eserlerinden biridir. Bu metni derslerimde kullandıktan sonra, 30 Ocak 2024'te oyun yazarı Hanson ile elektronik posta ile iletişime geçerek oyunun daha iyi anlaşılması ve okumaların zenginleştirilmesi amacıyla kendisine birkaç soru yönelttim ve 6 Şubat 2024 tarihinde yanıtlarını aldım. Oyun, fark edilebilir bir konuya sahip olması dolayısıyla, seyirciyi bir akış içinde yönlendirebilmektedir. Üstelik anlam ararken özsel felsefeyi ve belirsizliği de barındırmaktadır. Varoluşçuluğa göre insan, kendi kontrolü olmaksızın ilgisiz bir dünyaya doğar, sonrasında kendi eylem ve deneyimleriyle, değerlerini ve kişiliğini inşa eder. Özsel anlayışa göre ise, insanı diğer varlıklardan ayıran bir öz vardır ve bu öze sahip olduğu için insan olarak adlandırılır. *Godot'yu Beklerken* de dâhil olmak üzere çoğu uyumsuz oyunlar, anlamsız bir hayatta ve nedensiz bir dünyada anlam aramanın anlamsızlığını doğrudan veya dolaylı olarak incelemekte ve sorgulamaktadır ve bu nedenle uyumsuz oyun yazarlarının gündeme getirdiği konular genellikle varoluşçu felsefenin kapsamına girmektedir. Ancak bu makale *Godot'yu Beklerkeni Beklerken* adlı oyunda özsel anlamı ortaya çıkarmayı amaçlamaktadır. Çalışma, oyundan alınan diyaloglar aracılığıyla özseli ortaya çıkarmayı ve okuyucuya farklı bir bakış açısı kazandırmayı hedeflemektedir.

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1. Introduction

Waiting for Waiting for Godot (2016) (hereafter, *WFWFG*) is one of the most renowned works of the new generation of American playwrights by the actor and comedian Dave Hanson, who is relatively unknown to scholars. It is a biographical and award-winning two-act play penned as a parody of Beckett's seminal work *Waiting for Godot* (1953). The literature survey demonstrates that no academic study has been carried out on Hanson's *WFWFG*. However, it has "received rave reviews from *The New York Times* and *Time Out New York*, among others, and was a smash hit at the 2013 New York International Fringe Festival, earning the Overall Excellence in A Play Award" (*WFWFG*, 2016, back cover). Besides, the play offers a unique perspective, suggesting that "the only people who truly understand Beckett's *Waiting for Godot* are the understudies..." (*WFWFG*, 2016, back cover). This fresh interpretation has intrigued audiences and critics alike. Moreover, *The New York Times* described it as "delectable." It has also been staged in London, Istanbul, Antalya, Los Angeles, Budapest and Boston.

2. Rationale Behind the Study

Drama, one of the oldest genres of literature, is the closest to life, so dramatic texts are a significant means of teaching. Teaching dramatic texts in educational settings has recently become a popular field of interest to many scholars and educators mainly because:

Drama does things with words. It introduces language as an essential and authentic method of communication. Drama sustains interactions between students within the target language, creating a world of social roles and relations in which the learner is an active participant ... The language that arises is fluent, purposeful and generative because it is embedded in context. (Kao & O'Neill, 1998, p. 4)

While teaching selected plays on existentialism and essentialism, I assigned Beckett's *WFG* and Hanson's *WFWFG* to undergraduate and graduate literature students. I observed that the rarity of sources, such as academic papers, critiques, and analyses, particularly on *WFWFG*, stuck the students in existentialist assumptions. In light of this, I reached out to playwright Dave Hanson¹, whose assistance I hope will bring new perspectives and insights to the discussions.

Beckett's *WFG* has been interpreted and analysed mainly from existentialist and religious perspectives, especially by using themes and motifs associated with Christianity, mainly because of the content of the play exemplified in statements such as "The two men [Vladimir and Estragon] feel the need for true community [Christian community] and want it, yet they are unwilling or unable to pay the price" (Via, 1962, p. 34). While some literary critics such as Harold Bloom and James Roberts associate such abstract notions with existentialist philosophy by citing the characters' incapacity to comprehend the world rationally and logically, Michael J. Bennett, an expert on Beckett and the Theatre of the Absurd, reads *WFG* from an essentialist perspective: "In *Waiting for Godot*, essence precedes experience and, thus, Beckett's thought is a version of Cartesian Rationalism, not existentialism" (Bennett, 2011, p. 40). He attempts to free *WFG* from its absurdist chains and gives the audience a different reading perspective.

¹ On January 30, 2024, I contacted playwright Dave C. Hanson and asked him questions to better comprehend the play and its premise, and enrich this study with his invaluable comments. Accordingly, I received Dave Hanson's answers to the questions by email on February 6, 2024. Hanson's responses are given in the appendix.

I argue that *WFWFG* is not directly about existentialism, and it compels the reader to find life-fulfilling elements to make life meaningful; as Hanson states, “So they [characters] exist in a space where the artist’s condition has meaning. But as they progress through the story, they realize their own ideals and the very rules they’ve lived by may have lost their meaning, or they were doing them incorrectly,”² so I suggest reading the play through the lens of essentialism rather than analysing it from an existentialist perspective. In this play, Hanson distorts the traditional dramatic conventions through which the audience is familiarized. Because of its relatively complex, philosophical, and structural nature, it can hardly be put into a suitable category. Accordingly, Hanson argues:

I would say my play explores a microcosm within Beckett’s world—the existential crisis of an artist. I suppose it diverges some from Beckett’s pure absurdism. Mine is a more philosophical absurdism rooted in society’s rules about life and art and what happens when you live outside those rules.

WFWFG has a discernible plot, so it orients the audience. Moreover, it embraces essentialism and uncertainty while seeking meaning. The play breaks down language, so Val and Ester’s dialogues are contrary to reason and logic, and the sound is somehow nonsensical to the audience—the interactions’ uncertainty and ambiguity cause anguish, a common subject in absurd plays. Val and Ester’s interactions are repetitious and sparse. The play’s form is significant because it parallels humankind’s search for meaning.

3. Literature Review

Homo sapiens have aspired to know the world around them and discover who they are since they ascended to the world. This aspiration has been one of the most insatiable human adventures and endeavours to arrive at a convincing meaning and knowledge. Humankind’s quest for knowledge and meaning has never stopped. This relentless pursuit, while noble, can also lead to existential angst and a sense of never being satisfied. Likewise, Boorstin (1983) notices, “more appealing than the knowledge itself is the feeling of knowing” (p. 92). It emphasizes the vitality of man’s never-ending quest for knowledge and knowing. Human beings have never found their knowledge about the world and themselves gratifying enough to arrive at the ultimate truth and the meaning of life, so they endeavour to take their search for meaning beyond their limits. As “Man’s search for meaning is the chief motivation of his life” (Frankl, 1992, p. 106), humankind’s quest for knowledge and meaning seems never to stop so long as the uncertainties of their lives remain.

Humankind has sought answers to their questions about the nature of things in philosophy, religion, and literature. The twentieth century has produced several avant-garde playwrights such as Beckett, Adamov, Ionesco, Genet, and Pinter, to name a few. These playwrights significantly differ from the traditional dramatists in identifiable ways, treating knowledge, meaning, and vision regarding the world as absurd. German drama critic Martin Esslin coined the term absurd in his remarkable work *The Theatre of the Absurd* (1961) and defined the term absurd as “it strives to express its sense of the senselessness of the human condition and the inadequacy of the rational approach by the open abandonment of rational devices and discursive thought” (1961, p. 20). It challenges rational movements and traditional forms and styles. Besides, Styan (1981) defines this term as a man trapped in a meaningless and hostile universe offering no perspective of hope but for solitude, silence, and purposelessness (p. 126). Furthermore, absurd theatre reflects the sense of the senselessness of the human condition in

² See appendix for the quotes with no page number extracted from the email interview conducted with Dave C. Hanson, unless otherwise indicated.

a post-war world in which human beings are unable to find the meaning of their lives and are “deprived of certainties” (Meserve, 1965, p. 356). Most absurd plays directly or indirectly examine and question the futility of seeking meaning in a meaningless life and irrational world; the issues the absurd playwrights raise fall into the scope of existentialist philosophy. However, this article aims to explore the essentialist meaning of *WFWFG*.

4. Findings

Essentialist meaning derives from Aristotle's dictum: *Essence precedes existence*, whereas existentialist meaning is based on Sartre's concept that *existence precedes essence*. The *APA Dictionary of Psychology* defines essentialism as “in philosophy, the position that things (or some things) have essences; that is, they have certain necessary properties without which they could not be the things they are.” In addition, the essentialist perspective contends that meaning is an intrinsic phenomenon for individuals (Oderberg, 2007, p. 150). Essence is a set of innate characteristics and properties that make something what it is. Accordingly, in *WFG*, Vladimir compactly says, “The essential doesn't change” (Beckett, 1954, p. 14). Moreover, John Locke defines essence as:

Firstly, Essence may be taken for the being of any thing, whereby it is what it is. And thus, the real internal, but generally, in substances, unknown, constitution of things, whereon their discoverable qualities depend, may be called their essence. *Secondly*, the learning and disputes of the schools, having been much busied about genus and species, the word essence has almost lost its primary signification; and instead of the real constitution of things, has been almost wholly applied to the artificial constitution of genus and species. (Locke, 1825, p. 304)

WFWFG depicts two elusive characters, Val and Ester, who blatantly parallel Beckett's Vladimir and Estragon. They are understudies for Beckett's *WFG* production. They are waiting backstage for the director, who is unseen and a real person of unspecified gender, to call them up. Unlike Beckett's Vladimir and Estragon, Val and Ester have a purpose and passion to act. Whereas “Nobody is scratched in *Waiting for Godot*, but nobody gets started either” (Bloom, 2008, p. 1), Hanson's characters desperately wait for their turn to act. Besides, they question how precarious their lives are as understudies. Hanson states, “They hope for a situation in which they can finally perform, and when that opportunity presents itself, they're not sure the sacrifice was worth it. Even the performance, if they take it, is far less than what they dreamed it would be.” It demonstrates that they must sacrifice and suffer for their art, though it may not be worth it.

Val and Ester impatiently await their turn in the dressing room backstage. Ester speaks about the importance of Beckett's play and prides himself in the production with the anticipation of his possible appearance on the stage. When Val asks if he has known Beckett, Ester answers, “No, not physically. But that's the state of things, I'm afraid. The greats are dead and have been replaced with sophomoric reinterpretations of things that have already been seen. Nothing new, nothing to be done! It's the very reason I stopped doing film!” (Hanson, 2016, p. 16). His utterance prioritises the essence of things because of the impossibility of creating the new and replacing the preceding things. Humans essentially imitate the very essence of the late greats, who determine the ideal. This contention obliterates the dictum that *existence precedes essence*. Their essence negates the characters' futile existentialist struggle.

Existentialism posits that humans first exist, then construct their values and personalities by their actions in a disinterested world that they have been thrown out of. This view makes it inescapable for humans to take responsibility. Essentialism, on the other hand, suggests that

human beings have an essence that differentiates them from other things, leading them to imitate what they are exposed to due to their innate and essential nature. This situation is illustrated with the example of the acting profession. The following dialogue vividly portrays Val and Ester's incapability to act and take responsibility, bringing to life the real-life implications of these philosophical concepts.

VAL: You're just repeating what they say over and over again?
ESTER: *You're* just repeating what they say over and over again.
VAL: You're *just* repeating what they say over and over again?
ESTER: You're just *repeating* what they say over and over again. (Hanson, 2016, p. 21, emphasis in original)

The extract astutely demonstrates the aspects of essentialism. Although the understudies repeat the sentence, the only difference they make is the intonation given in italics. It signifies the futility of the action they take to construct their selves, i.e., one is what or who one is. This very fact displays an anti-existentialist leaning toward the understudies' position, so I could argue that they are solidified men of essence. Their respective emphatic difference symbolises their essence as humans. However, they repeat what others say to them and imitate.

Toward the end of Act One, Laura, an assistant stage manager, steps backstage and is bombarded with the understudies' questions. Val wonders:

VAL: How is it out there, on stage? How is the performance?
LAURA: It is what is.
VAL: Maybe the second act will be better?
LAURA: Won't make any difference.
VAL: Maybe it's the acting. Perhaps if two other actors were to step in the production would be...
LAURA: No. The acting is acting. They have no idea what the play is about. (Hanson, 2016, p. 33)

Laura's tautological responses are mere examples of essentialism because she finds the performance and acting profession as what genuinely they are. She attributes no subjective aspects and, thus, prioritises the *whatness* of things rather than *thatness*, i.e., essence. However, while their conversation continues, she disparages the acting profession, so Ester protests against her. She reflects her essentialist leanings towards the profession. She responds, "Well, it isn't. You wear a costume someone else made, you stand where someone else tells you, and then you say lines someone else wrote. What is the big deal?" (Hanson, 2016, p. 34). No matter what is attributed to the performance or acting, nothing makes sense to what they are. They are what they are concerning their very essence. In other words, they are the product of their essence. Laura's attitude lays bare this stark reality to the understudies.

Laura protests and claims that her position as an assistant stage manager in the production is more compelling and demanding than acting in *WFG*, and even "deaf puppets using sign language could perform it" (Hanson, 2016, p. 36). Val, whose aspiration has been shattered by her response, begins to question the following:

VAL: Of course, it does! Think about it! Deaf puppets implies several truths about our existence. One, we're all just dangling on strings controlled by fate or God or the universe, none of us having actual free will. Deafness expresses our inability to address the pain of life and our own mortality. And sign language for puppets would be almost impossible to understand which would further emphasize how the human race really is just a bunch of deaf, blind creatures incapable of truly understanding each other while we wait around to die! I mean, Beckett could hardly express it better! (Hanson, 2016, p. 36)

Val's essentialist questioning explicitly reveals the incapacity of humans to actualise themselves and the fact that they are destined to live within the confines of some spiritual entities or the universe. They lack the freedom or capacity to construct themselves and exist. Thus, they are devoid of responsibility. Their essence is nothing more than deafness, blindness and disinterestedness to one another. Humans are essentially miserable creatures, struggling to fill their time by engaging in busy themselves because nothing can be done to change the ever-standing course. Beckett mirrors the very fact of humans' essence with his non-physically entrapped and motionless characters in *WFG*. Hanson states, "Their [Val and Ester's] inaction is Beckett's action." Beckett explicitly demonstrates that human essence is inevitably a desperate condition seeking ways to stride but to fail better in every trial. Besides, Val and Ester's actions do not change their essence. Hanson exhibits this human essence to show them how to fail better. "Something could happen!" (Hanson, 2016, p. 40), a contrary claim to "nothing to be done" of *WFG*, indicates a speck of hope for a plausible change and seeking meaning in the lives of the understudies. Bennett contends, "Beckett's characters find affirmation in responding to the world" (Bennett, 2012, p. 1). Thus, Vladimir and Estragon respond to their world by engaging in philosophical conversations. Hanson's characters try to find affirmation in responding to the *biş* as Ester says, "The Entertainment business" (Hanson, 2016, p. 20). When the lights in the theatre shut off, the understudies attempt to act by saying their lines, but to no avail. Upon failure to act, they look at one another motionlessly. They are stranded in limbo between their imagination and inaction, so I put the play's premise as "deep essentialist anguish."

5. Conclusion

Literature, particularly drama, explicitly or implicitly deals with human concerns and their quest for meaning and knowledge, and dramatic texts in English are highly effective language devices loaded with philosophical underpinnings as they vividly reflect expression planes, offering a rich diversity of purposive communication. These texts also play a significant role in the development of literacy. The literariness of dramatic texts resembles a conversation with various contextually generated effects, such as insult, sarcasm, humiliation, and praise.

Moreover, they challenge readers to make direct or indirect interpretive inferences, stimulating their intellect and encouraging a deeper understanding of drama's situationally contextualised language materials. Understanding and interpreting dramatic texts can enlighten language learners, deepening their knowledge of the language and its cultural context. I contend that the pedagogical use of authentic dramatic texts could greatly develop language learners' language skills, particularly their oral skills, by adding philosophical dimensions to their reading experiences. For such purposes, *WFWFG* is an outstanding play with its linguistic repertoire and philosophical undertones that await further analysis and instructional use.

Note on Ethical Issues

The author confirms that the study does not need ethics committee approval according to the research integrity rules in their country (Date of Confirmation: 30/05/2024).

Conflict of Interest

The author declares no conflict of interest.

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Appendix.

Author: What was your motivation to write “Waiting for Waiting for Godot”? Would you describe it as a kind of parody of Beckett’s seminal work “Waiting for Godot”?

Dave Hanson: First off, it is a parody. The idea for the play first came to me when I was, myself, acting as an understudy in a production of WFG. This was in Los Angeles, California in the early 2000’s. I was a young, new actor looking to do any job that seemed like acting work. I was cast as an understudy and immediately felt out of my depth, like most actors, when approaching Beckett’s work. As we moved closer to the opening night, I had a lot of anxiety about having to perform- I was not prepared, I had had limited rehearsal time, I didn’t really understand the character(s) or the play itself and everything was building towards a real life version of *The Actor’s Nightmare*. But then I never went on. And for two months I sat around backstage 3 nights a week and 1 Sunday matinee, with anxiety, high hopes and the boredom of being an understudy... which is sort of what the play is about. So I saw an instant parallel of the life of an actor with the characters on stage in Beckett’s story. It all made sense then. After that it was just pulling from my experiences as an actor and writer- getting advice from other artists who were just as ignorant as I was, dealing with all the things you seemingly are missing out on as your friends from back home start families and buy houses etc. The sacrifice of being an artist and pursuing this career.

A: To many drama critics, Beckett’s work explores existentialist themes. To what extent does your work share similarities or diverge from a philosophical perspective and character drawing?

DH: I would say my play explores a microcosm within Beckett’s world- The existential crisis of an artist. I suppose it diverges some from Beckett’s pure absurdism. Mine is a more philosophical absurdism rooted in society’s rules about life and art and what happens when you live outside those rules. At the end, I think Beckett was making an important point about our existence. I am trying to make a less important reference joke about my own life (and the life of an artist). To quote myself “A sophomoric re-interpretation of things that have already been seen. Nothing new! Nothing to be done!”

A: Can you elaborate on the significance of the title in relation to the notion of “waiting” which is a central theme in both your play and Beckett’s? And how does the title of your play exhibit the essence of “waiting”?

DH: It’s a simple play on the name and the life of an understudy- In a play about waiting, the only ones doing something are the actor’s cast in the leads performing the waiting. The understudies, whose job is to wait in anticipation that they’ll be needed, are actually living what the play is about. Their inaction is Beckett’s action. And so they fill time with repetitive (and useless) preparation, exercising their craft, plotting their rise to fame, just to end up sitting in silence as they listen to the lead actors perform via the sad (but necessary) speaker that all theatres have backstage.

A: Characters, once properly drawn, propel a plot’s direction. How do your characters engage with essentialist notions of meaning? And do they regard meaning as something inherent and fixed?

DH: My characters exist within the confines of a dressing room backstage of a theatre- so their reality is one of fixed times (calls to arrival, to opening, intermission, etc) and their meaning (or purpose) is fixed for the first act- They both have a job to do, waiting. And as they wait we discover that one character has knowledge (or so it seems) while the other is naive and inexperienced, seeking knowledge to the question: how do I make it as an actor (or how do I exist)?

This need for answers propels the naive actor out beyond the dressing room where he returns with an opportunity and knowledge- his meaning or purpose has changed much to the displeasure of his partner. This crisis leads them to ask what the purpose or meaning to all of it is and is it even worth it? What have they and will they miss out on for this sacrifice to a dream and to art? For all their high thinking and romanticism of the sacrifice of the artist, the reality is sacrifice hurts- and all of the schooling, preparation and rule following can't save you from that pain of artistry (or the pain of life). Is it worth it? That's the question.

A: Do you think there is an interplay or tension between essentialist and existentialist perspectives in your play?

DH: I think it's a constant battle between the two for these characters as it is for most artists, unless you are one of those people who come from money or developed with a view that material things or a traditional life don't matter all that much.

What I remember most from my time in LA (where I worked a lot) was the high ideals of the struggling actor, who expressed his love and commitment to excellence of craft, who would throw all of that away if it meant becoming a financially successful actor. Many times in LA you would work on someone's passion project, be it for film or theatre, only to have an actor drop out in a heartbeat because they booked a commercial or a guest starring role on a hit TV show and would have to miss the day of the performance or the shoot. The same is true for New York City (where I live now) but overall here the craft of art is taken more seriously and given more room to become something worth committing to.

A: In my view, the essence of the play somehow contributes to the human condition in a world that seems to have lost its sense and meaning long ago. Do you think your characters represent this condition and seek meaning and fulfillment?

DH: Yeah, my characters and my setting are a place where the belief of a proper artist condition could exist- the stage is where the art of writing and acting and directing all come from. So they exist in a space where the artist's condition has meaning. But as they progress through the story they realize their own ideals and the very rules they've lived by may have lost their meaning or they were doing them incorrectly. They hope for a situation in which they can finally perform, and when that opportunity presents itself, they're not sure the sacrifice was worth it. Even the performance, if they take it, is far less than what they dreamed it would be.